

Efficient Machining Solutions for Sustainable Aircraft Production

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Abstract

This article deals with sustainability in aviation industry. Sustainability aspects are explained concerning operation of aircrafts, future aircraft concepts and the manufacturing of machined integral parts. Here, adapted raw materials, machining strategies, NC-simulation and use of machine tool aggregates lead to improvements in the shop floor footprint and sustainability.

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Keywords: sustainability, aircraft, machining, NC-simulation, raw material

1 Extended Abstract

Sustainability has become the most challenging strategic goal for the next decades to stop climate change. In aviation sustainability is now an important part of business strategies and operations - whether through products, industrial sites or people. Specific targets for the main fields of sustainability are clearly defined by timeline and key performance indicators like reduction of CO₂-emission, energy, waste etc. for products and industrial footprint including the supply chain.

Civil air traffic produces roughly 2% of overall CO₂-emission caused by humans [1]. New aircraft concepts, more efficient turbofans and developments based on hydrogen propulsion are massively forced. Airbus has the ambition to develop the world's first zero-emission commercial aircraft by 2035. Earlier CO₂-emission reductions can be achieved by fostering a full value-chain in Europe to produce synthetic sustainable aviation fuel (SAF). The objective for commercial aircraft is to achieve certification of 100% SAF in flight by 2030 [1].

When looking closer to the production of aircrafts, of course, the structures, their materials and manufacturing methods become more important. Bionically inspired lightweight designs lead to optimized aircraft structures and parts, while Aluminum alloys compete with composite based materials for application. Composites might have advantages concerning weight but disadvantages concerning recyclability and cost. Sustainable low-cost lightweight structures might be realized by mainly using Aluminum material with best recyclability. Beside composite and Aluminum, Titanium, Inconel and steel parts will still be used for high temperature and/ or for high stress applications [2].

Due to very high part variety for aircraft integral parts with relatively small batch sizes, machining out of plate material is still widely in use with a high ratio of scrap, up to 98% [2]. Despite sorted recycling of chips and remaining material of clamping connections has been implemented for years, more near net shape raw material like die forgings, extrusions, castings and additive manufactured blanks will alternatively be fostered to minimize material and machining energy resources. Especially two additive manufacturing methods are under development: metal powder bed fusion and wire welding. Premium AEROTEC is already qualified for manufacturing parts made by Titanium powder bed fusion and delivers for example manifolds for the A320-

family [3]. In addition, Premium AEROTEC produces serial flying parts made from plasma wire welded raw material (so called DED parts; DED := Direct Energy Deposition)

For the machining processes several new approaches and developments will lead to more sustainability. However, in the price driven global market for machined parts sustainability just starts to become a unique selling point. High performance machining technologies enables higher material removal rates with higher outputs per machine. According to the Kienzle equation, higher feed rates cause less energy consumption per removed material volume. E.g. for Aluminum machining, doubling the feed rate reduces energy consumption of a milling cutter by more than 15% per part [4].

It is well known, that most of the energy consumption of machine tools are caused by aggregates. Here, especially coolant supply systems are in focus for energy savings. Frequency-controlled coolant medium pumps improve efficiency [5]. Today, machining operation specific coolant pressures can be chosen in NC-programs. Current developments in technological NC-simulations of milling processes will enable a calculation of current loads of operations with minimized coolant flow rates that are actually needed. Of course, specific energy control systems will more and more adapt energy consumption to different modes.

Hard metal machining leads to high tool wear. For Titanium machining Premium AEROTEC investigated tool wear depending as a function on cutting conditions like cutting speed, feed per tooth and width of cut. The developed tool wear model implemented in the technological NC-simulation enables a prediction of tool wear and simulated tool life times for the different machining operations in serial production [6]. Another research project deals with an automatic tool wear measurement for solid carbide milling cutters to minimize the removed material when regrinding. The overall target for reduction of the resource solid carbide by these activities is - 30%.

The technological NC-simulation is another enabler to improve sustainability in machining. For new parts, that have to be produced, already optimized NC-programs reduce the number of iterative evolutions to qualify NC-programs ready for serial production. By using technological NC-simulation, milling loads can be optimized, chatter can be detected and also tool deflection can be visualized [5]. More efficient milling processes with better part quality, less scrap and shorter machining times per part lead to more sustainability.

2 References

- [1] AIRBUS homepage, <<https://www.airbus.com/en/sustainability>>
- [2] Lange, M.: Herausforderungen bei der spanenden Hochleistungsbearbeitung metallischer Flugzeugbauteile. In: „Spanende Fertigung“, 5th edition: Biermann, D. Vulkan-Verlag Essen, 2012, p.67-76
- [3] Premium Aerotec druckt für A320 in Serie, Nordwestzeitung, May 11th 2022
- [4] Surmann, T.: Simulation der Dynamik von Dreh- und Fräsprozessen; professorial dissertation, Technical University Dortmund, Vulkan Verlag, Essen, 2017, ISBN 978-3-8027-8794-2
- [5] Hülsemeyer, L.: Energieeffizienz spanender Werkzeugmaschinen und bedarfsgerechter Betrieb am Beispiel der inneren Kühlschmierstoffzufuhr; Dissertation, Leibnitz University Hannover, IFW reports, edition 06/2016, ISBN: 978-3-95900-093-2
- [6] Surmann, T., Lange, M., Dege, Jan: Verschleißbewertung und –modellierung, WT Werkstattstechnik, edition 112 (2022) Nr. 01-02